

Deliverable D4.1

Validated suite of tools for assessing fish origin, quality (freshness) and safety, including detection of antibiotics, toxins and pathogens

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Table of Contents

1. Executive Summary.....	4
2. Assessing Fish Origin.....	5
2.1 Comparison of data from microbial targeted sequencing.....	5
2.2 Stable isotopes.....	7
2.3 Genetic markers and associated costs.....	8
Genetic markers and associated costs	8
2.4 Integration of data.....	9
Aquaculture (farmed) vs. wild-caught fish.....	9
2.5 K-mers identification for aptamer-based sensors through microbial untargeted metagenomic analysis.....	14
Advantages of working with k-mers.....	14
Methods.....	15
Results	15
3. Assessing Fish Freshness and Safety.....	16
3.1. Safety and pathogens.....	16
Results	17
4. Antibiotics (Resistome)	19
5. Toxins	21
6. Conclusions	22
7. Outputs	23
8. References	25

1. Executive Summary

This report summarizes the work carried out in WP4, including the methods developed, the integration and comparison of data, and the potential applications of the results. The main goal of WP4 was successfully met by testing a range of analytical approaches on seafood samples provided by the Living Labs (LLs), using protocols established and refined in earlier deliverables.

The findings presented here draw from several technologies—microbiome analysis, stable isotope profiling, and genetic methods—and explore how these tools can be applied in practice. For instance, short DNA sequences obtained through untargeted sequencing of seafood-associated microbiota are examined for their potential use alongside the aptamer sensors developed in WP5.

Untargeted sequencing proved especially valuable, helping to identify microbial markers for origin authentication and assess the presence of antimicrobial resistance genes (the resistome). In terms of microbial safety, results from pathogen screening are included in this report and discussed further in Deliverable D6.3.

While some of the results have been shared in previous deliverables, they are revisited here to provide a complete overview of the collaborative work conducted across the project's various partners.

2. Assessing Fish Origin

2.1 Comparison of data from microbial targeted sequencing

As reported in deliverable D4.2, microbiological methods demonstrated a high efficiency in discriminating fish samples based on their origin and method of production (wild vs farmed). Statistical analysis done on the distribution of bacterial ASVs (uniquely identified sequences) produced a set of organisms whose abundance distribution allow us to identify them as markers. These organisms could be used for the development of primers sets for Real-Time PCR as identifiers of a particular fishing site/farming site.

From the first analyses, a lower diversity was observed for cultured samples, with the exception of samples from Malta (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Diversity indices across wild and cultured samples from different sites

To compare microbial communities' structure across samples, Bray-Curtis distances were used. As shown in the Non-Metric Multidimensional Scaling (NMDS) plot, the comparison among wild samples showed fewer differences among fishing sites (Figure 2, left), compared to the ones observed for farmed samples, with the latter resulting in a highly accurate distinction among origin sites (Figure 2, right).

Figure 2. NMDS plots of wild (left) and farmed (right) samples

A differential abundance analysis was performed to detect the ASVs which are responsible of the observed differences among sites. Some of the obtained taxa were then selected, based on their presence and abundance distribution, as marker taxa.

For farmed samples, 7 marker ASVs were found, while for wild samples 8 informative marker ASVs were retrieved. The distribution of the two sets of ASVs across samples makes them good identifiers of fishes from different origins.

Figure 3. Marker taxa for farmed fishes. The ASV marked as BASE is an artificial ASV with random assigned abundances between 0.1 and 0.11 across samples to allow the model to run in the presence of zeroes

Figure 4. Marker taxa for wild samples. The ASV marked as *BASE* is an artificial ASV with random assigned abundances between 0.1 and 0.11 across samples to allow the model to run in the presence of zeroes

A new set of data, obtained by a new sample collection performed by Living Labs has been obtained. These samples have been already processed and sequenced according to procedures. However, since samples arrived in the first week of May, analysis of data is still being performed. Sequences have been uploaded to European Nucleotide Archives (ENA) under the following accession number: PRJEB78552.

2.2 Stable isotopes

The robustness of the stable isotope approach, combined with elemental analysis, has also been demonstrated for discriminating between wild and aquaculture fish, as well as identifying the region of production. This is described in more detail in *D4.4: Protocol for Fish Authenticity and Origin Based on the Stable Isotope Approach*. The FishEUTrust traceability system, which includes stable isotope analysis, has three key steps:

1. Development of suitable analytical methods
2. Establishment of a database of authentic samples
3. Data processing using chemometric approaches.

The developed protocol has been tested on wild and farmed fish and mussel samples from several countries, including Malta, Portugal, Spain, Slovenia, and Croatia. The IsoFoodTrack database serves as a centralized repository for storing and analyzing the extensive data generated. Advanced statistical analyses, such as LDA, OPLS-DA, and DD-SIMCA, have enabled precise classification and discrimination of samples based on their production method and geographical origin.

Figure 5. Relationship between $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ and $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ in farmed and wild fish fillets from different countries

accuracy reached 75%. Notably, isotopic values tend to be lower on average in the Mediterranean region (Malta, Slovenia, Croatia) compared to the Atlantic region (Portugal, Spain). The inclusion of elemental composition further improved the accuracy of determining the country of origin. The study also validated the origin of fish samples from Portugal using DD-SIMCA. This classification model demonstrated high sensitivity (93%) and excellent specificity (98%), with an overall accuracy of 96%.

While Stable Isotope Ratio Analysis (SIRA) shows great potential for origin discrimination, it also has limitations, specifically in geographical origin discrimination. These can be addressed by integrating additional parameters, such as microbiome data. This aspect is discussed in detail in *Chapter 2.4: Integration of the data*.

2.3 Genetic markers and associated costs

Genetic markers and associated costs

The major goal of this work was to test the possibility of assigning an individual to its population/group of origin with a certain probability. To this end, we used the “AssignPOP” bioinformatic tool as described in the previous report. It performs population assignment using a machine-learning framework. This approach generates an SNPs reference baseline and then assigns “unknown” samples (that were not part of the dataset used to generate the baseline) to one population with a certain probability. The result of assigning “unknown” samples to one of the identified populations and the associated posterior probability is reported in Fig. 6 (below). It well summarizes the high accuracy of the correct assignment of each sample to its population of origin; however, it is worth noting that for the SNPs analysis, it is necessary to have available a SNPs array that, for seabream, was produced in previous projects. Moreover, the cost of this kind of analysis using the SNP array platform was about 60€ per sample. This could be reduced (40-50€/sample) if the number of specimens to genotype is in the order of 350, which is the number of samples that can fit in an array plate.

Key findings include the ability to differentiate between wild and farmed fish using only two isotopic markers, with higher $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ values observed in wild specimens (Fig. 5). This method is efficient and cost-effective, as both analyses can be performed simultaneously at a cost of only 30 EUR per sample.

Furthermore, using only stable isotope data, OPLS-DA successfully differentiated fish according to their country of production, with $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ identified as a key discriminating parameter. When both production methods were included, the overall classification

Figure 6. Assignment of “unknown” samples to their origin groups using AssignPOP. Each bar shows the posterior probability of membership in one of six groups (M_A, M_W, P_A, P_W, S_A, S_W)

2.4 Integration of data

Aquaculture (farmed) vs. wild-caught fish

We analyzed a total of 115 individual fish specimens, each characterized by a suite of chemical and biological measurements. Specifically, for every sample we recorded four stable-isotope ratios ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$, $\delta^{34}\text{S}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ -water) alongside concentrations of 20 trace and major elements. Complementing these geochemical profiles, we also generated comprehensive metagenomic data for each specimen. Out of all samples, 15 were missing metagenomic data and were thus left out. (SPA01 - SPA15). Additionally, 30 samples were classified as “wild-with an error in labelling” and were selected to be in the validation set. The 70 samples left were then split using 5-fold stratified split. So the final five splits included 56 samples in the training set and 14 in the test set.

Our primary objective was to develop a robust binary classifier capable of distinguishing between aquaculture (farmed) and wild-caught fish. To this end, we selected two tree-based algorithms - Decision Tree (DT) and Random Forest (RF) - owing to their interpretability and strong performance on tabular datasets. Each model was trained and evaluated under three distinct input scenarios, always employing the same five train/test splits to ensure a fair comparison:

1. **Isotope + trace elements data only**
 - Three isotope ratios + 20 elemental concentrations ($\delta^{18}\text{O}$ -water was removed due to many missing values)
2. **Metagenomic data only**
 - Features derived exclusively from microbial community profiles
3. **Combined data**
 - All isotope, elemental, and metagenomic features pooled

By contrasting these configurations, we aimed to quantify the added value of metagenomic markers relative to traditional isotope- and element-based indicators, and to determine whether an integrated approach yields superior classification accuracy.

Isotope + trace elements data only

Whether we used decision trees or random forests to classify samples based on the 23 features (three isotopes plus 20 trace elements), we consistently achieved perfect accuracy—an indicator of overfitting. In fact, further analysis showed that these features intrinsically distinguish aquaculture from wild specimens, so training a machine-learning model is unnecessary for such a clear-cut separation. To demonstrate this, we pooled all samples from both the training and test sets, reduced their dimensionality with t-SNE, and plotted them in two dimensions. The resulting scatter-plot (Fig. 7) clearly shows that these 23 features alone are sufficient to separate aquaculture and wild species.

Figure 7. t-SNE dimensionality reduction of all fish samples represented with three isotopes and 20 trace elements

Metagenomic data only:

Attributes 1–15															
Fold	Attr 1	Attr 2	Attr 3	Attr 4	Attr 5	Attr 6	Attr 7	Attr 8	Attr 9	Attr 10	Attr 11	Attr 12	Attr 13	Attr 14	Attr 15
Fold 1	ASV-197	ASV-327	ASV-328	ASV-346	ASV-100	ASV-525	ASV-12	ASV-414	ASV-252	ASV-730	ASV-282	ASV-49	ASV-445	ASV-556	ASV-1029
Fold 2	ASV-197	ASV-328	ASV-327	ASV-346	ASV-49	ASV-247	ASV-266	ASV-445	ASV-87	ASV-282	ASV-24	ASV-21	ASV-100	ASV-1029	ASV-333
Fold 3	ASV-327	ASV-197	ASV-328	ASV-525	ASV-247	ASV-21	ASV-24	ASV-535	ASV-445	ASV-414	ASV-730	ASV-87	ASV-127	ASV-49	ASV-228
Fold 4	ASV-346	ASV-525	ASV-100	ASV-266	ASV-535	ASV-730	ASV-247	ASV-449	ASV-414	ASV-21	ASV-49	ASV-24	ASV-252	ASV-445	ASV-282
Fold 5	ASV-197	ASV-327	ASV-328	ASV-346	ASV-12	ASV-525	ASV-100	ASV-24	ASV-247	ASV-21	ASV-414	ASV-730	ASV-252	ASV-535	ASV-153

Attributes 16–30															
Fold	Attr 16	Attr 17	Attr 18	Attr 19	Attr 20	Attr 21	Attr 22	Attr 23	Attr 24	Attr 25	Attr 26	Attr 27	Attr 28	Attr 29	Attr 30
Fold 1	ASV-87	ASV-228	ASV-980	ASV-615	ASV-244	ASV-748	ASV-787	ASV-1012	ASV-63	ASV-47	ASV-550	ASV-261	ASV-44	ASV-365	ASV-316
Fold 2	ASV-535	ASV-169	ASV-252	ASV-556	ASV-12	ASV-230	ASV-1031	ASV-615	ASV-244	ASV-748	ASV-127	ASV-712	ASV-449	ASV-728	ASV-447
Fold 3	ASV-282	ASV-900	ASV-266	ASV-615	ASV-371	ASV-12	ASV-449	ASV-50	ASV-63	ASV-96	ASV-20	ASV-6	ASV-33	ASV-365	ASV-556
Fold 4	ASV-87	ASV-365	ASV-228	ASV-615	ASV-1029	ASV-12	ASV-244	ASV-556	ASV-441	ASV-153	ASV-127	ASV-637	ASV-242	ASV-447	ASV-152
Fold 5	ASV-186	ASV-228	ASV-1029	ASV-341	ASV-351	ASV-266	ASV-20	ASV-66	ASV-6	ASV-127	ASV-449	ASV-674	ASV-748	ASV-129	ASV-365

Figure 8. Selected metagenomic features for each training fold

Using metagenomic data, the situation changes. Because we have far more metagenomic features than samples, we first reduce their number before training a binary classifier. To this end, we selected 30 features using a method that computes the absolute Pearson correlation matrix on the training set, calculates each feature's mean absolute correlation with all others, sorts features by ascending mean correlation, and retains the 30 least-correlated features (See Fig. 8, which features have been selected for each of the five folds). Five-fold cross-validation yielded an accuracy of 78.8% for decision trees (SD 14.2%) and 83.5% for random forests (SD 12.6%). These results indicate that the metagenomic feature set is not as powerful as the isotope + element set, and that the classifier's performance is not robust - its accuracy depends heavily on the particular train/test split.

Since the accuracy still remains high ~80%, we proceed with further analysis by identifying the most important metagenomic features for each fold based on the RF model (see Fig. 9).

Figure 9. The most important features to distinguish between aquaculture and wild fish samples for five folds

Combined data

When we combine the 24 isotope and element features with 16 selected metagenomic features, the classifiers again achieve perfect accuracy. However, this result is driven entirely by the strong predictive power of the isotope and element data, making the metagenomic features unnecessary.

Origin prediction (Malta, Portugal, Spain)

Then, we leverage the same dataset to infer each fish's country of origin rather than whether it's farmed or wild. For this multi-class classification task, we again employ Decision Tree and Random Forest algorithms to sort the samples into one of three categories: Malta, Portugal, or Spain. The results have been tested on the same 5 train and test splits. Accuracy, together with its standard deviation across the splits, is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Accuracy of Decision Tree and Random Forest with different input data, together with its standard deviation across the splits.

Data	Decision Tree	Random Forest
<i>Isotopes + elements</i>	92.8% (Sd. 4.5%)	97.0% (Sd. 5.7%)
<i>Metagenomics data</i>	61.7 % (Sd. 17.1%)	73.0% (Sd. 6.6%)
<i>Combined data</i>	95.6 % (Sd. 5.8)	94.0% (Sd. 9.0%)

The findings show that, regardless of the modeling technique, isotopes and trace elements offer the greatest predictive power. Models built solely on metagenomics data suffer in both accuracy and robustness—reflected by larger standard deviations, especially in the Decision Tree. However, combining metagenomic with isotope and trace-element data restores high accuracy, matching the performance achieved using only isotopes and trace elements.

Additionally, Figures 10, 11, and 12 display t-SNE projections of all fish samples under three scenarios (isotopes + elements, metagenomics, and combined). Figures 10 and 12 show clear separation by origin, whereas Figure 11 (metagenomics only) fails to reveal distinct clusters based on origin.

Figure 10. tSNE visualization using 23 isotope and trace elements

Figure 11. tSNE visualization using metagenomic data

Figure 12. tSNE visualization using combined data (isotope and trace elements and metagenomics)

Comment:

Note on validation: the current datasets were artificially combined by JSI group. For a more robust evaluation, all measurements should be obtained from the same individual fish specimens in future studies.

2.5 K-mers identification for aptamer-based sensors through microbial untargeted metagenomic analysis

Advantages of working with k-mers

Genetic marker species identification is often a complex and time consuming process. Traditional procedures are typically DNA extraction, amplification, and sequencing followed by long bioinformatic analyses including read quality control, scaffold and MAG assembly, taxonomic classification, and statistical analysis for the identification of markers.

To make this process simpler and faster, we designed a workflow and a related R package - MarkUS ("Marker K-mers for Untargeted Sequencing", available at <https://github.com/AldoDale/MarkUS>) - that is particularly designed to identify genetic markers from relatively short DNA pieces. This approach bypasses genome assembly and taxonomic annotation using the k-mer analysis method that involves the investigation of short nucleotide sequences of length k.

The workflow has been applied, and shown to work successfully, in identifying signature k-mers with different fish origin points and spoilage state. Group-specific short sequences are promising for downstream uses such as use as aptamers to build biosensors for use in environmental monitoring.

Methods

Sequencing was conducted on an Illumina NovaSeq platform via an untargeted metagenomic approach. Raw reads were pre-processed to ensure relevance and quality of data: CUTADAPT for primer trimming, Sickle for quality-based trimming, and Bowtie2 for removal of host-derived DNA sequences.

For each sample, paired-end FASTQ reads were merged, and k-mer counting was done with Jellyfish, with a k-mer size of 20 bases, selected for suitability in sensors design. For focusing on group-specific markers, k-mers which occurred in $\geq 80\%$ of samples of a group but not at all in any other group were retained.

To enhance the informativeness of resultant sequences, Shannon entropy was calculated for each k-mer that was kept, and only those sequences whose entropy was greater than 1.95 were selected. This served to remove low-complexity or non-informative sequences.

Moreover, edit distance filtering was used to prevent the labelling of very similar sequences as distinct markers and to reduce the impact of sequencing errors and the occurrence of natural mutations. K-mers with three or fewer nucleotide differences (edit distance ≤ 3) from any sequence in another group were removed.

Finally, redundant sequences were removed for further dataset optimization to make sure that the remaining k-mers are unique and informative genetic markers that can be used in downstream procedures like the creation of biosensors.

Results

Traceability

From the k-mer analysis, a number of marker 20-mers (k-mers of length 20) were retrieved. For Malta, 3870 markers were found, while 42 were found for Spain and 20 for Portugal. These results reflect the geographical disposition of the fishing sites, with Spain and Portugal being close to each other and showing the presence of a low number of unique k-mers, indicating that this approach might be accurate for this type of investigation. The k-mers obtained can be used to produce aptamer-based sensors able to discern among fishes imported from different regions.

Malta: 3870 markers	Spain: 42 markers	Portugal: 20 markers
[1] ACCGAAATTTGGCACCGTTG	AAACGGCCITTAAGTTGGCC	AACTGAAACCCCTTTGGGTAC
[2] ACCGATAATGTTGGTGGCCAG	AACGCATTGGGTAACCTGGT	AAGTCAACCGGCTCGATTGT
[3] ACCGATCAAGTGGTCCCTTG	AATGAATTGGTCCCCAGGT	ACCACCTTTGGGACATGTG
[4] ACCGATGCGAGTTGTTCAAG	ACCRAACGGAATTTGGTGGT	AGCCCGAATTAAGTGTCTCG
[5] ACCGCAATCAGGTAGGTTTC	ACTCATCCGAGCTATGGAGT	AGCCCTTTAGAAAGGGATC
...	ACTTCAAAATCCGGGCGCAT	AGGACACTGTTCCCGCATG
[3866] TGCCCGTTAAGTAATGGCCA	ACGAAATCCCTTGGTGGTGA	ATCCCAAGGGTTGGTCACAT
[3867] TGCTACTGATAAGCTGGCCA	AGSTTAAACCCCGTTACATGG	CCGGATACGGTTAAATGTG
[3868] TGGAAGTGTACATCTGGCCA	ATACCGCCGAGTCCITTAAG	CCGGATTTTACGATAGCGG
[3869] TGGAAATTCAGCCGTAGCCA	ATCGTAGGCTCCGACGATA	CGAAATAGGCGCTTTGGCCA
[3870] TGGAGTCATCATATCGGCCA	ATGGCTAAGCTCCCTTTAAG	CGTTTAGTCCGATCGGCCA
	ATGGTAACCTTATGGCCCGCA	CTATCGTTTGCAGCGCGGA
	ATTAACGGCCGACGTTATG	GATTAGTATTAGCCCGGCC
	ATTTGATCGAACGGACTCG	GATTTGGCGATGTCGAAACA
	ATTTGAACTACGGGAGCCG	GCAGGGTTATTTGCCCGAAA
	CAGGTGCCGTCAGGTAATTA	GGAACTCATTITTCGCCGA
	CATTAGGATCGTGGGCCAA	GGATTACCAATTTACGCCGA
	CCAAATGATAGCGGGTTTC	GGTCCGCAACGTAACCTGTA
	CCAAATTTGGCAATCAACCC	TACCTAAGTTGGCCGAGTA
	CCCTTGGCTAGCAGGATTA	TGCGGACTTGGCCAAATTA
	CCCTTTTTGAAAAGGCGCC	
	CCGTTCCAAAGATAGTGTGG	
	CGACATATACGGGTATCCG	
	CGCCAGTTAAGTTCAAGCG	
	CGCGGGTAGATCTACTTACA	
	CTAAATCTGGGGCTCTCTAA	
	CTAATAATTAGCGCGGTGCC	
	CTCGAAGTCCCTTGGAAATGA	
	GAACCCGGCATTITTCGGA	
	GAATCCGTTGCAATCGAAATC	
	GGAAACGGCTATATTTCCG	
	GGAAAGCTCCAGCTTTGTAC	
	GGCCGTTCCAAATTTCCAG	
	GGTGTGAATAGTCCCTACAC	
	GTGCCCTCGGCCATATAAAC	
	GTTCCGTCAAACCTCTGAGA	
	GTTGTACCCGATAAGCCCA	
	TAGGAACTCGGTACCCGTC	
	TCCGTAATTCAGGCCGCTGAA	
	TCCGCTGTCTCCAAATTAGA	

Figure 13. DNA markers found for the different fishing sites

Freshness

From the analysis conducted for the freshness experiment, 97 markers were found to be unique and informative for t0 (fresh fish), while 328 markers were found for t2 (spoiled fish). The presence of such a high number of markers for t2 is explained by the deep changes the microbiota underwent during the 3 days of conservation. As per the traceability experiment, the k-mers are suitable for the development of a kit for sensors to detect fish freshness *in loco*.

t0: 73 markers

```
[1] 20 AACAAATGGAGCTTCAGGTTG
[2] 20 ACAACCTGAAGCTCCATTGT
[3] 20 ACAGGATGTCTGCCAACTAG
[4] 20 ACATTACCTCAGCTGGAGG
[5] 20 ACTAGGCCCTGCACGATATGA
... ..
[69] 20 GTAGATTCTCACTGAAGGCA
[70] 20 GTAGCGCGTCTGACTCCAGA
[71] 20 GTAGGAGACCATGTCCTTCA
[72] 20 GTGAATCCAGAGGCTGTACA
[73] 20 GTGGACACCTGCGGCTTATA
```

t2: 255 markers

```
[1] 20 AACAAATGGAGCTTCAGGTTG
[2] 20 AACACAGCCTCTGATTGGTC
[3] 20 AACAGAGCCATCGTTAATGT
[4] 20 AACATCAAGCGTCTTATGGA
[5] 20 AACGCTTCCGATGGTACATC
... ..
[251] 20 TCAGAGACGTCGCTGTTACA
[252] 20 TCTGAGGTTGCTACACATAA
[253] 20 TGATTCAGTGTCTAGACGCA
[254] 20 TGTCTGGATAAGCGCCAACA
[255] 20 TTCTCACTGTGTTAGCAGAA
```

Figure 14. DNA markers for fresh fish (t0) and spoiled fish (t2)

3. Assessing Fish Freshness and Safety

3.1. Safety and pathogens

Importance of microbial safety in seafood

Seafood is significantly more perishable than terrestrial foods, making it particularly vulnerable to microbial contamination. The natural decomposition of organic and inorganic matter, driven by microbial activity, results in the spoilage of seafood. (Gram and Dalgaard; 2002). In addition, seafood could be contaminated by human pathogens. Without proper handling and transport practices, foodborne pathogens and spoilage microorganisms can proliferate rapidly along the supply chain, leading to accelerated quality degradation. (Prabakhar et al., 2020) Spoilage is primarily associated with gram-negative bacteria, such as psychrotolerant genera *Pseudomonas*, *Shewanella*, and *Photobacterium*, whose growth results in the production of off-putting odors. Zoonotic infections can also occur by known human pathogenic bacteria such as *Vibrio* ssp., *Mycobacterium* ssp., *Campylobacter* ssp., *Legionella* ssp., *Staphylococcus* ssp. (Brauge et al., 2023). Other bacterial species are mainly fish pathogens, e.g., *Aeromonas*, *Streptococcus* (Evans et al., 2006). Given the microbial diversity of marine environments, freshly harvested seafood inevitably carries a certain microbial load. Therefore, effective product management is essential to inhibit the rapid growth of spoilage organisms and opportunistic pathogens.

Short methods overview

Here, Next Generation Sequencing NGS methods were employed to detect potentially pathogenic and specific spoilage organisms (SSOs). To do this, gDNA was extracted from wild and farmed seabreams (*Sparus aurata*) gill samples received from LLs (Malta, Portugal, Spain), which were used to amplify bacterial marker 16S rRNA (V3-V4 hypervariable regions). Amplicons were purified and sequenced using platform Illumina MiSeq. Obtained reads were processed, removing forward and reverse primers, and merged. Taxonomic classification was performed using Silva Reference database (Quast et al., 2012), as depicted in Deliverable D4.2.

P Detected pathogens and SSOs were quantified, and their relative abundances computed using R software. In a parallel freshness-assessment experiment (also detailed in D4.2), European seabass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) specimens sourced from a local supplier were stored at 4 °C for three days. Daily samplings from the same individuals were conducted, with spoilage levels evaluated in tandem by the Quality Index Method (QIM) as described by Larsen et al. (1992). (QIM, Larsen et al., 1992).

Figure 15. Bar plots representing relative abundances for ten bacterial genera with known pathogenic or spoilage potential in seabream samples from Malta, Portugal and Spain, for wild specimens (top) and farmed specimens (bottom). Each bar represents a single sample (indicated by the ID on x-axis), and color-coded segments indicate the proportion of reads assigned to each genus; cumulative bar height corresponds to the total fraction of pathogenic genera in that sample

Results

From the complete bacterial sequence dataset, we focused on ten well-characterized genera that include known pathogens and specific spoilage organisms: *Vibrio*, *Streptococcus*, *Staphylococcus*,

Shewanella, *Photobacterium*, *Mycobacterium*, *Legionella*, *Francisella*, *Campylobacter*, and *Aeromonas*. Figure 15 summarizes the relative abundances of these genera in wild (Fig. 15a) and farmed (Fig. 15b) gilthead seabream. In wild specimens, the combined abundance of these ten genera remains below 0.4 % of the total bacterial community. Maltese samples are dominated by *Aeromonas* and *Shewanella*, whereas Portuguese and Spanish samples show a predominance of *Staphylococcus*. Moreover, the pathogen profiles of Spain and Portugal are more similar to one another than to Malta, likely reflecting their closer geographical proximity. Farmed seabream exhibit an even lower cumulative abundance of these genera, lightly reflecting wild specimen bacterial communities.

Figure 16. Redundancy-analysis (RDA) showing how variation in relative abundance of ten potentially pathogenic or spoilage related bacterial genera structures microbial communities in seabream samples from Malta, Portugal and Spain. Samples (points) are colored by country, and arrows represent each genus' contribution to the RDA axes: direction indicates which samples are enriched in that genus, and arrow length reflects its explanatory power. wild specimens (left); farmed specimens (right)

Redundancy analysis (RDA; Fig. 16) supports these observations by illustrating how each bacterial genus constrains sample ordination. In the wild-caught group (Fig. 16a), Maltese samples plot furthest along the *Aeromonas* vector, whereas Portuguese and Spanish samples are pulled toward the *Staphylococcus*, *Vibrio*, and *Streptococcus* arrows. Conversely, farmed fish (Fig. 16b) exhibit a more even sample distribution: Portuguese fish cluster along the *Staphylococcus* vector; Spanish fish align with *Photobacterium* and *Mycobacterium*; and Maltese fish remain associated with *Shewanella*. The length of each arrow reflects the strength of its influence on community composition, confirming geographical and rearing-related shifts in pathogen and spoilage-organism profiles.

In the seabass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) freshness experiment, analysis of the microbiota demonstrated rapid community reshaping over cold storage. When focusing on pathogenic and spoilage-associated genera, distinct diversity patterns emerged over time (Fig. 17). At T0 (immediately after purchase), these taxa displayed low and heterogeneous relative abundances across samples. By T1 (24 h) and T2 (48 h) at 4 °C, *Photobacterium* spp. had overtaken the microbial community, consistent with its well-documented role in seafood

spoilage. Simultaneously, other genera—such as *Shewanella* spp.—fell to negligible levels, likely outcompeted by the explosive growth of *Photobacterium*. These temporal shifts mirror the spoilage progression detailed in Deliverable D4.2.

Figure 17. Bar plots representing relative abundances of ten bacterial genera with known pathogenic or spoilage potential in seabass samples. Each bar represents a single sample (indicated by the ID on x-axis), and color-coded segments indicate the proportion of reads assigned to each genus; cumulative bar height corresponds to the total fraction of pathogenic genera in that sample. Samples are facet according to time of sampling: 0, day of purchase from supplier; 1, one day after purchase; 2, two days after purchase.

4. Antibiotics (Resistome)

Trimmed metagenomic reads were analysed using Nonpareil, which estimates average sequencing coverage based on read redundancy within each dataset. Subsequently, antibiotic resistance profiles were inferred using the Resistance Gene Identifier (RGI), which predicts resistome composition from nucleotide or protein sequences by leveraging both homology-based and SNP-aware models.

RGI analyses were performed using the Comprehensive Antibiotic Resistance Database (CARD) as a reference framework. Output data for each sample were imported into R for downstream analysis.

Resistance gene abundances—annotated as Antibiotic Resistance Ontology (ARO) terms or grouped by Drug Class—were statistically compared using the DESeq2 package using default options. Visualisations were generated using ggplot2.

Nonpareil analysis revealed that samples FEUC2 and FEUE6, following host DNA removal,

exhibited insufficient sequencing depth to support robust downstream analyses and were therefore excluded from the dataset. After filtering, the mean estimated coverage across the remaining samples was approximately 61% (Fig. 18)

Figure 18. Non-pareil results

Alignment against the CARD database resulted in the detection of numerous Antibiotic Resistance Ontology (ARO) terms per sample. To ensure high-confidence identifications, only those AROs with > 90% sequence identity to the reference were retained, yielding a total of 342 unique resistance genes.

Comparison between timepoints T0 and T2 indicated a notable enrichment at T2 of specific resistance genes, particularly CRP and aadA5, with this trend being especially pronounced in the Scottish samples (Fig. 19).

Figure 19. Hierarchical clustering of antimicrobial-resistance gene presence across seabass samples from Croatia and Scotland over three storage times (T0, T2). Coloured bars above the heatmap indicate storage time (T0 = cyan, T2 = magenta) and origin (green = Croatia, pink = Scotland). Heatmap cells show gene abundance (yellow = 0, purple = 100, red = 400), with genes CRP and aadA5 highlighted.

The CRP gene is linked to resistance against macrolides, fluoroquinolones, and beta-lactam antibiotics such as penicillin, while *aadA5* confers resistance to aminoglycosides. Geographical comparisons of T0 samples revealed distinct biogeographical signatures in resistome composition (Fig. 3). Spanish samples, for instance, showed higher relative abundance of *LpsA*, associated with resistance mechanisms against peptide antibiotics. In contrast, Scottish samples were enriched for multidrug resistance genes conferring resistance to peptide, macrolide, fluoroquinolone, aminoglycoside, carbapenem, cephalosporin, and beta-lactam antibiotics (Fig. 20).

Figure 20. Hierarchical clustering of enriched antibiotic-resistance genes across seabream samples. Coloured bars over the heatmap indicate the sample's origin. Colour of the heatmap cells shows the genes' abundance across samples.

5. Toxins

The topics of the research carried on by WP5 was to develop rapid, sensitive and selective biosensors to detect target biotoxins as okadaic acid (OA) and saxitoxin (STX) in seafood. For this purpose, we developed a miniaturized screen-printed carbon electrodes modified with gold nanoparticles and a polymer to improve their features. Then, enzyme-linked aptamer assays were developed basing on a competitive format (WP5).

As the final application of the developed sensors is to detect marine toxins, such as OA and STX, in mussels, key experimental parameters were studied and optimized to achieve the best performance possible. The first step was the pretreatment of mussels to properly extract OA and STX from this complex matrix.

The procedure is listed as follows:

- Washing of the mussels with deionized water and left to dry
- Grinding and homogenizing the mussels with a blender
- Mixing a portion of the homogenized mussels with an 80% (v/v) methanol solution by shaking well
- Centrifuging the suspension for 10 minutes, collection of the supernatant, then filtration with the aid of a syringe
- Diluting appropriately the extract in the working buffer and analysing it with the developed sensor

This last step was further optimized, as solutions containing a fixed amount of OA or STX were prepared in mussel extracts at different dilution factors, with 1:5 factor resulting the most appropriate to be used.

Then, contaminated mussel samples were firstly grouped by dimensions, then extracted following the aforementioned procedure and finally analysed by means of the electrochemical sensors for toxins detection developed in WP5. The results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Toxins detection in mussel samples by the developed aptamer-based sensors

Group n.	OA (ng/mL)
1	0.70 ± 0.14
2	0.31 ± 0.07
3	0.23 ± 0.05
4	0.48 ± 0.10
5	0.75 ± 0.15

As it can be seen, the reported results are related to OA presence in the samples, while the obtained values for SXT were not significative.

6. Conclusions

In conclusion, the work carried out in WP4 has delivered a robust, multi-disciplinary toolbox for seafood origin and freshness assessment and safety monitoring that integrates advanced molecular, chemical, and computational techniques.

The NGS-based molecular analyses are consistent with published studies. We detect a low background of spoilage and pathogen-associated bacteria in samples, slightly more elevated in wild specimens. This is expected due to the heterogenous microbial condition of open marine environment. Using high-throughput sequencing technologies, we are able to identify the spectrum of opportunistic pathogens and spoilage related taxa and quantify their relative abundances. All this information obtained by sequencing data, coupled with untargeted sequencing data, allows us to select specific DNA aptamers for incorporation into biosensors platforms, allowing rapid detection. This will combine the rapid possibility of detection allowed by sensor to the robustness of NGS sequencing.

Stable isotope and elemental fingerprinting demonstrated that the ratio between two key isotopes ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{15}\text{N}$), especially when supported by $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ and trace-element data, can classify production method and provenance with over 90 % accuracy at a per-sample cost of under €30, and chemometric modelling further enhanced discriminative power.

Genetic population assignment using AssignPOP confirmed these findings at the host level, with SNP-array-based classifiers achieving >95 % assignment accuracy, though at a higher per-sample expense. Our integrative machine learning analysis compared the isotopic/elemental data, which efficiently discriminated between farmed and wild samples, with the metagenomic one, which was the most accurate to assess the origin of fish. Results showed an increased performance when the two approaches are combined, highlighting the accuracy and the importance of an integrated approach.

The K-mer analysis proved to be a strong tool for the identification of marker sequences, providing a high number of markers for both fish origin and freshness assessment, ready to be used as aptamers for sensors. Also in this case, fish from geographically close fishing sites resulted to be more similar to each other (i.e., Spain and Portugal). The same pattern was observed for the presence of pathogens, which show a geographically-related distribution.

The resistome profiling produced 342 high-confidence antibiotic-resistance genes in seafood microbiota, with CRP and aadA5, linked to multi-drug resistance, enriched during spoilage (T2), and CRP and LpsA dominating Scottish and Spanish samples, respectively. These results demonstrated both temporal and geographic genetic signatures.

In parallel, our biotoxins-detecting sensors for okadaic acid and saxitoxin achieved sensitive, reproducible detection in mussel extracts with minimal preparation.

Collectively, these findings establish a comprehensive FishEUTrust traceability platform that is technically validated, cost-efficient, and ready for field deployment. The implementation of aptamers power into biosensors holds the promise to develop a rapid, easy to use, unexpensive tool that could be used in the fish market origin and quality assessment.

Future work will focus on co-sampling individual specimens to harmonize all omics and chemical measurements, optimize real-time sensor integration, and scale our protocols across broader species, countries of origin, and supply-chain contexts.

7. Outputs

PUBLICATIONS:

Nerini M, Russo A, Decorosi F, Meriggi N, Viti C, Cavalieri D, Marvasi M. A Microbial Phenomics Approach to Determine Metabolic Signatures to Enhance Seabream *Sparus aurata* Traceability, Differentiating between Wild-Caught and Farmed. *Foods*. 2024 Aug 28;13(17):2726. doi: 10.3390/foods13172726.

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SUBMITTED ARTICLES:

Russo A, Pavlovič B, Nerini M, Marvasi M, D'Alessandro A, Cardazzo B, Martino M, Cavalieri D, Ogrinc N, Patarnello T. 2025. Isotopes, genetic markers and microbial communities: tools for seafood traceability. A review. *Reviews in Fisheries Science and Aquaculture*. Submitted for publication May 2025.

D'Alessandro A, Russo A, Cavalieri D, Bacci G. 2025. MarKUS: An R package for the fast identification of marker k-mers. *Proceedings of the 20th Computational Intelligence methods for Bioinformatics and Biostatistics (CIBB) congress, 2025*, under review for short paper publication.

CONTRIBUTIONS IN CONGRESSES

- Oral presentations

“Metagenomic tools for Seafood Traceability and Freshness”. D’Alessandro A, Russo A, Meriggi N, Cerasuolo B, Renzi S, Ugolini A, Cavalieri D. 54th Congress of the Marine Biology Society (SIBM), June 9-12, Naples, Italy

- Poster presentations

“Microbial communities to assess the traceability and freshness of seafood: A metagenomic approach”. Russo A, D’Alessandro A, Meriggi N, Cerasuolo B, Renzi S, Ugolini A, Marvasi M, Cavalieri D. - International Union of Microbiological Societies (IUMS) Congress 2024, Florence, Italy.

“16S rRNA targeted metagenomic sequencing to assess seafood traceability and freshness”. Russo A, Nerini M, D’Alessandro A, Meriggi N, Cerasuolo B, Renzi S, Ugolini A, Patarnello T, Martino M E, Marvasi M, Cavalieri D. - Italian Zoological Union (UZI) Congress, 2024, Pisa, Italy.

“Comunità microbiche per la tracciabilità e la freschezza del pesce: un approccio metagenomico”. Russo A, D’Alessandro A, Meriggi N, Nerini M, Cerasuolo B, Renzi S, Ugolini A, Marvasi M, Cavalieri D - Italian Society for Marine Biology (SIBM) 2024, Rome, Italy - Best poster award winner.

“Seafood traceability: Geographic origin of *Sparus aurata* and *Dicentrarchus labrax* investigated through gills microbiota”. Russo A, Meriggi N, Cerasuolo B, Renzi S, Nerini M, Ugolini A, Marvasi M, Cavalieri D - Italian Zoological Union (UZI) Congress, 2023, Palermo, Italy.

“Authentication and traceability of fish and seafood using stable isotope and multielemental approach”. Pavlovič B, Strojnik L, Potočnik D, Mazej D, Terro C, Ogrinc N - V: KUZMIČ, Nina (ur.), et al. *15th Jožef Stefan International Postgraduate School Students’ Conference, 31st May - 2nd June 2023, Kamnik, Slovenia: Book of abstracts*. Ljubljana: Jožef Stefan Institute: Jožef Stefan International Postgraduate School, 2023. Str. 19. http://ipssc.mps.si/auxiliary_material/BoA%20IPSSC%202023.pdf.

“Authentication and traceability of fish and seafood using stable isotope and multi-elemental approach”. Pavlovuč B, Strojnik L., Potočnik D, Ogrinc N. - V: OGRINC, Nives (ur.), et al. *2nd ISO-FOOD Symposium from Food Source to Health: book of abstracts: Portorož, Slovenia, April 24-26, 2023*. 1st ed. Ljubljana: Jožef Stefan Institute, 2023. Str. 42, ilustr. ISBN 978-961-264-268-6.

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